

THE PREVALENCE AND ASSOCIATED FACTORS OF ERGONOMIC ISSUES AND WORK-RELATED MUSCULOSKELETAL DISORDERS AMONG OPERATING THEATRE STAFF IN A TERTIARY CARE CENTRE MARDAN, PAKISTAN

Mian Habib Ullah Bacha¹, Muhammad Shahzeb², Fawad Khan³, Majid Javed⁴, Abdul Aziz⁵, Dr. Nasir Ali⁶, Asad Khan^{*7}

¹BS Anesthesia Technology (BKMC) – Lecturer, Zia Institute of Nursing and Allied Health Sciences, Mardan, Pakistan.

²Lecturer Radiology, College of Medical Technology BKMC Mardan

³BS Anesthesia Technology – College of Medical Technology, Bacha Khan Medical College (BKMC), Mardan, Pakistan.

⁴BS Anesthesia Technology – College of Medical Technology, BKMC, Mardan, Pakistan.

⁵BS Anesthesia Technology – College of Medical Technology, BKMC, Mardan, Pakistan.

⁶Associate Professor MLT, College of Medical Technology BKMC, Mardan

⁷Lecturer Anesthesia, College of Medical Technology, BKMC Mardan

^{*7}asadipms@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17470563>

Keywords

Ergonomics, Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders, Operating Theatre, Cognitive Workload, Occupational Health, Pakistan

Article History

Received: 10 September 2025

Accepted: 16 October 2025

Published: 29 October 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *
Asad Khan

Abstract

Background: Healthcare workers in operating theatres (OTs) are highly exposed to physical, cognitive, and organizational stressors that lead to ergonomic issues and work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WRMDs). These problems affect staff well-being, patient safety, and overall healthcare efficiency. Despite global recognition of these risks, little evidence exists from Pakistan, particularly in the tertiary care settings of Mardan.

Objectives: This study sought to determine the prevalence of ergonomic issues and WRMDs among OT staff in tertiary care hospitals in District Mardan and identify associated demographic, physical, cognitive, and organizational risk factors.

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out among 165 OT professionals, including surgical and anesthesia staff, at Mardan Medical Complex. Stratified random sampling was used. Data were collected via a validated questionnaire assessing demographic information, workload (NASA-TLX domains)(1)(2)(3), physical ergonomics, cognitive ergonomics, and organizational ergonomics. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, and Pearson correlations in SPSS. Statistical significance was set at $p < .05$.

Results: Musculoskeletal pain during shifts was reported by 89.1% of staff, with 87.3% reporting lower back pain. Major risk factors included prolonged standing (35.2%), poor workstation design (27.3%), and repetitive tasks (26.7%). High mental demands were reported by 35.8% of staff, while 34% experienced

significant temporal workload. Years of experience showed a negative correlation with both physical and cognitive workload ($p < .05$).

Conclusions: Ergonomic challenges and WRMDs are widespread among OT staff in Mardan, consistent with international trends. Targeted interventions such as improved workstation design, staff training, shift adjustments, and organizational support are urgently required.

INTRODUCTION

The health sector prioritizes patient safety and outcomes, yet the occupational well-being of healthcare providers often receives insufficient attention (4)(5). Operating theatres (OTs) are among the most ergonomically demanding environments in hospitals, where surgeons, anesthesiologists, nurses, and technicians are exposed to extended hours of standing, repetitive procedures, and high cognitive loads(6)(7) (8). These conditions increase the risk of work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WRMDs), cognitive strain, and organizational stressors that may compromise both staff health and patient safety(9) (10)(11)(12)(13)(14)(9).

Ergonomics is the science of optimizing the interaction between humans and their work environment, considering physical, cognitive, and organizational dimensions(6) In healthcare, ergonomic design of equipment, procedures, and workspaces is essential for minimizing occupational hazards, enhancing efficiency, and ensuring long-term sustainability of the workforce(15)(12). Despite advancements in ergonomic interventions in high-income countries, healthcare facilities in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) such as Pakistan often lack formal ergonomic guidelines and resources (16)(17)(18)(19)(20)(21).

Musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) are a significant occupational health problem worldwide, particularly in surgical and anesthetic specialties.(22) These include injuries or discomfort in muscles, tendons, ligaments, joints, and nerves, commonly manifesting as lower back pain, shoulder strain, or neck stiffness (22). In healthcare, MSDs contribute to absenteeism, decreased productivity, and early retirement, imposing heavy economic and clinical costs (23)(24)(25)(26)(27). Lower back pain (LBP) is especially prevalent, with international studies

reporting rates ranging from 47% to 80% among surgical staff (28)(29)(30)(31)(32).

In Pakistan, where resources are limited and occupational health policies remain underdeveloped, ergonomic challenges in OTs have not been systematically studied. District Mardan, despite being served by tertiary-level hospitals, lacks evidence on ergonomic risks among OT professionals. This study addresses this research gap by quantifying the prevalence of ergonomic issues and WRMDs and examining associated factors among surgical and anesthesia staff in a tertiary care centre in Mardan.

Literature Review

Global Burden of Lower Back Pain (LBP):

LBP is one of the most commonly reported occupational health concerns among OT staff. A study in Saudi Arabia found that 61.4% of male and 38.6% of female OT professionals reported LBP, with surgeons and anesthesiologists being most affected (28). Similarly, an Indian study reported that 73.8% of nurses experienced LBP, largely due to prolonged standing and lifting patients (32). Research at Mansoura University (Egypt) revealed that obesity, female gender, and long working hours were significant predictors of LBP among OT staff (31). These findings highlight how demographic, behavioral, and occupational factors contribute to the development of LBP.

Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders (WRMDs):

WRMDs encompass a wide range of musculoskeletal injuries linked to occupational activities. Yizengaw et al. (2019) reported a 64.2% prevalence of WRMDs among Ethiopian OT staff, with LBP, hip, and shoulder discomfort most frequently reported(33). A study by Janki et al. (2017) found that 47.5% of surgeons reported

current musculoskeletal complaints, mainly affecting the neck (39.5%) and lower back (34.9%)(34). Similarly, research in Iran showed high rates of lumbar and knee disorders among surgical technologists (Isfahan Study, 2016). These studies emphasize the pervasive nature of WRMDs in surgical environments and the urgent need for ergonomic interventions.(33)(34)

Associated Risk Factors:

Several occupational factors exacerbate ergonomic risks. Hanif et al. (2019) demonstrated that prolonged standing led to leg pain (67%), LBP (54.4%), and muscle stiffness (45.5%) among healthcare staff. Among anesthesiologists, repetitive wrist actions, prolonged bending, and poor workstation ergonomics were strong predictors of WRMDs (35). Gender differences were also observed, with women reporting higher rates of upper back and shoulder discomfort (33). Poor shift scheduling, lengthy workdays, and a lack of control over job duties are organizational hazards that lead to nurses' weariness and stress(36)(37). These findings underscore how task design, shift patterns, and demographic attributes interact to elevate ergonomic risks. Ergonomics, aimed at optimizing the relationship between individuals and their work environment, has been underappreciated in anesthetic practices but is gaining recognition as a crucial element of healthcare.(38)(39)

Ergonomics in Anesthetic Practice

Ergonomics plays a central role in anesthetic safety and efficiency. Modern anesthesia workstations incorporate adjustable controls and alarms, yet ergonomic gaps remain. Poorly designed layouts and a lack of supportive equipment contribute to fatigue and cognitive overload (15). International guidelines emphasize proper posture, adjustable monitors, optimal OT temperature and lighting, and manual handling training to reduce WRMDs (World Health Organization [WHO], 2017). However, such measures are often absent in LMIC healthcare facilities like Pakistan.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: This research employed a descriptive cross-sectional design to assess the prevalence and associated factors of ergonomic issues and WRMDs among OT staff.

Study Setting and Duration: The study was conducted at Mardan Medical Complex, a tertiary care facility in District Mardan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Data collection occurred over 4–6 months following ethical approval from the College of Medical Technology (BKMC) Research Committee.

Population and Sample Size: The target population included surgical and anesthesia staff working in OTs. Based on a total OT staff population of 284, a sample size of 165 was calculated using OpenEpi with a 95% confidence interval and 5% margin of error. Stratified random sampling ensured proportional representation of surgical staff (n=141) and anesthesia staff (n=24).

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion: Surgeons, anesthesiologists, surgical nurses, technologists, and technicians with ≥ 1 year OT experience.

Exclusion: Administrative/support staff, radiology staff, temporary staff with < 1 year experience, and individuals with chronic pain or medical conditions unrelated to occupational ergonomics.

Data Collection Tool: A structured questionnaire with 57 items was administered. Including: Demographic data (age, gender, marital status, BMI, experience, work hours, shifts). NASA-TLX workload dimensions (mental, physical, temporal demands; effort; performance; frustration). Physical ergonomics (postures, workstation design, musculoskeletal symptoms). Cognitive ergonomics (cognitive overload, concentration, decision-making), Organizational ergonomics (teamwork, breaks, shift scheduling). The questionnaire incorporated validated ergonomic assessment tools (1)(35)

Data Analysis: Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 22 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive statistics, including means, standard deviations, frequencies, and percentages, were computed to summarize participant characteristics and study variables. Associations between demographic characteristics and ergonomic outcomes were evaluated using the Chi-square test for categorical variables and independent-sample t-tests for continuous variables. Pearson's correlation coefficient was applied to assess relationships among continuous variables. A two-tailed p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Research Committee of the College of Medical Technology, Bacha Khan Medical College, Mardan. Participation was entirely voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection. Confidentiality and anonymity of the participants were strictly maintained throughout the study.

Results

This study assessed the prevalence of ergonomic challenges and work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WRMDs) among 165 operating theatre (OT) staff in Mardan. The findings are presented below, supported by descriptive tables and figures summarizing the key results.

Baseline Characteristics: The study population comprised predominantly males (83%) with a mean age of 32.3 ± 7.1 years. The average BMI was 26.0 ± 3.6 , indicating an overweight trend. Participants had a mean professional experience of 7.2 ± 4.7 years and worked an average of 53.5 ± 15.9 hours per week; 55.8% were married. Shift distribution included 49.7% on day, 23% on night, and 26.7% on rotating shifts. Most participants worked in General Surgery OR (34%), followed by Neuro (15%), Orthopedic (13%), Gynecology & Obstetrics (12%), ENT (12%), ER (9%), and Eye OR (6%).

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics of Participants

Demographics	Values/Results
Gender (n, %)	Male 137 (83%), Female 28 (17%)
Age (mean \pm SD)	32.34 ± 7.1 years
BMI (mean \pm SD)	26.04 ± 3.63
Experience (mean \pm SD)	7.16 ± 4.72 years
Weekly work hours (mean \pm SD)	53.48 ± 15.9
Marital Status (n, %)	Married 92 (55.8%), Unmarried 73 (44.2%)
Shift Pattern (n, %)	Day 82 (49.7%), Night 38 (23%), Rotating 44 (26.7%), Other 1 (0.6%)
Workplace (type of OR)	Orthopedic OR (13.00%), G. Surgery OR (34.00%), Eye OR (6.00%), ENT OR (12.00%), Gyne and Obs OR (12.00%), Neuro OR (15.00%), ER OR (9.00%),

BMI; body mass index, n; frequency, %; percent, SD; standard deviation

Workload Assessment (NASA-TLX Domains): Most participants reported moderate levels of frustration (77.6%), with only 15.1% indicating low frustration. The majority (61%) perceived their performance as average, while 27% rated it as good and 12% as poor. Regarding workload,

70.3% described their effort as medium to high, and 72% experienced medium to high physical demands. Mental and temporal demands were also notable, with 35.8% and 34% of respondents, respectively, reporting medium-high levels.

Ergonomic Issues and WRMDs

Prevalence of Musculoskeletal Symptoms:

89.1% reported musculoskeletal pain during shifts. 87.3% specifically reported back pain.

- Prolonged standing: 35.2%
- Poor workstation design: 27.3%
- Repetitive tasks: 26.7%

Primary Risk Factors Identified:

WRMDs ergonomic issues	RESPONSE	Gender		Total	PREVALENCE (%)
		male	female		
	no	42	8	50	30.30
	yes	95	20	115	69.70
	Total	137	28	165	100
Pearson Chi-Square	0.048				

Cognitive Ergonomics: With an overall incidence of 40.2%, the data show that cognitive ergonomic problems are rather common among operating theatre (OT) professionals. Ineffective SOPs (53%), multi-tasking demands (58.8%), and inconsistent communication and poorly structured workspaces (65.7%) were the most common causes of cognitive strain. 40.6% of respondents said they frequently or almost always had mental tiredness during shifts, and almost half

(48.5%) said the design of surgical equipment increased cognitive burden. On the other hand, fewer participants considered training adequacy (28.6%) or information presentation efficacy (18.2%) to be troublesome. These results show that to increase performance and lessen mental tiredness among OT staff, better communication methods, ergonomic training, and cognitive workload management are required

Cognitive Ergonomic Issue	Prevalence (%)	Bar Representation
Inconsistent communication & poor workplace design	65.7%	
Multi-task demands	58.8%	
Ineffective standard operating procedures (SOPs)	53.0%	
OT environment	27.9%	
Effectiveness of information displayed	18.2%	
Overall Prevalence (Average)	40.2%	

Organizational Ergonomics:

Only 28% reported having adequate breaks during long surgeries. 65% noted insufficient organizational support for ergonomic practices. Communication and teamwork were rated as inadequate by 32%. According to the results, just 20% of respondents thought organizational processes were effective or better, while 41.2% said they were ineffective or extremely ineffective. In a similar vein, 36.4% of respondents said that their shift patterns supported work-life balance poorly or very poorly, which has a negative impact on employee well-being.

Approximately one-third of respondents reported ineffective protocols for unforeseen events, and 44.2% found duties unclear, indicating weak communication and planning. Inefficient resource use (24.2%), inadequate training (35.8%), and poor teamwork (38.2%) further reduced efficiency. Nearly half reported a lack of ergonomic guidelines (44.2%) and management support (46.4%). Regular ergonomics training (33.9%) and adjustable furniture (20.1%) were the most suggested improvements.

Discussion

This study reveals an alarmingly high prevalence of ergonomic issues and WRMDs among OT staff in Mardan, with nearly 9 out of 10 participants reporting musculoskeletal discomfort. The findings are consistent with international literature, where similar occupational groups report prevalence rates between 60–80% (33)(25).

Lower back pain emerged as the most common complaint, aligning with studies from Saudi Arabia (28)(29) and India (32). Prolonged standing, a dominant risk factor in our study (35.2%), has been similarly highlighted (22)(31), who linked extended standing hours with leg cramps, stiffness, and LBP.

The cognitive workload results also indicate significant mental strain, with over one-third

reporting medium-to-high demands. This resonates with (15) who observed heightened cognitive loads in anesthetists during critical procedures. Notably, our study also identified organizational shortcomings—insufficient breaks, limited teamwork, and inadequate institutional support—that likely exacerbate ergonomic burdens. Similar findings were noted in Ethiopian studies, where staff shortages and poor shift management increased WRMD risks (33)

A significant negative correlation between years of experience and workload perception suggests that senior staff may adapt better to ergonomic challenges, potentially through skill acquisition and coping mechanisms. Conversely, high BMI was positively associated with musculoskeletal

pain, supporting prior research that links obesity to heightened WRMD risk (31)

Limitations

This study has several limitations. Musculoskeletal pain and workload perceptions were self-reported, which may introduce recall or reporting bias. The cross-sectional design limits the ability to establish causal relationships, and the focus on District Mardan restricts generalizability. Additionally, the absence of real-time ergonomic assessments prevented objective evaluation of postures and movements.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study revealed a high prevalence of ergonomic challenges and work-related musculoskeletal disorders among OT staff in Mardan, with lower back pain as the most common complaint. Contributing factors included prolonged standing, poor workstation design, repetitive tasks, and inadequate organizational support. To mitigate these issues, ergonomic workstation redesign, staff training on workload and stress management, structured breaks, optimized shift rotations, and inclusion of ergonomic standards in hospital and national policies are recommended. Proactive implementation of these measures can enhance staff well-being, improve patient safety, and reduce absenteeism.

REFERENCES

- Hart SG. NASA-TASK LOAD INDEX (NASA-TLX); 20 YEARS LATER.
- Young G, Zavelina L, Hooper V. Assessment of Workload Using NASA Task Load Index in Perianesthesia Nursing. 2008;23(2):102-10.
- Clinical T, Education S. International Journal of Anesthesiology & Research (IJAR) ISSN 2332-2780 NASA Task Load Index Scale to Evaluate the Cognitive Workload during Cardiac Anesthesia Based Simulation Scenarios. 2016;4:300-4.
- Bailey CR, Radhakrishna S, Asanati K, Dill N, Hodgson K, McKeown C, et al. Ergonomics in the anaesthetic workplace: Guideline from the Association of Anaesthetists. *Anaesthesia*. 2021;76(12):1635-47.
- Saxena KN. Ergonomics and the Anesthesiologist. 2023;98-100. Available from: https://journals.lww.com/jica/fulltext/2023/02020/ergonomics_and_the_anesthesiologist.9.aspx2/8
- Vural F, Sutsunbuloglu E. Ergonomics: An Important Factor in the Operating Room. *J Perioper Pract [Internet]*. 2016 Jul 1 [cited 2025 Aug 23];26(7-8):174-8. Available from: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/1750458916026007-804>
- Mandal AC, Gundersen MAAG. Hospital ergonomics. *Tidsskr Danske Sygehuse*. 1977;53(5):74-90.
- Fujita Y. The IEA is challenging to create its future. *Zesz Nauk Politech Poznańskiej Organ i Zarządzanie*. 2017;(72):35-43.
- Ergonomics - Overview | Occupational Safety and Health Administration [Internet]. [cited 2025 Aug 23]. Available from: <https://www.osha.gov/ergonomics>
- Choobineh A, Movahed M, Tabatabaie SH, Kumashiro M. Perceived demands and Musculoskeletal Disorders in Operating Room nurses of Shiraz city hospitals. *Ind Health*. 2010 Jan;48(1):74-84.
- Narsigan S ET. Work Related Musculoskeletal Disorders among Nurses: Systematic Review. *J Ergon*. 2015;s4.
- Long MH, Johnston V, Bogossian F. Work-related upper quadrant musculoskeletal disorders in midwives, nurses and physicians: A systematic review of risk factors and functional consequences. *Appl Ergon*. 2012;43(3):455-67.
- Sheikhzadeh A, Gore C, Zuckerman JD, Nordin M. Perioperating nurses and technicians' perceptions of ergonomic risk factors in the surgical environment. *Appl Ergon*. 2009;40(5):833-9.

14. Rahgoshay N, Daneshmandi H, Seif M, Dokooohaki R, Shahbazi M, Sadeghian R, et al. Enhancing nurses' well-being: the effect of ergonomic interventions on work-related musculoskeletal disorders. *Int J Occup Saf Ergon*. 2025;
15. Pfeffer S, Maier T, Stricker E, Rall M, Trick M. Cognitive ergonomics and inforamatory load in anesthesia. *Biomed Tech*. 2012;57(SUPPL. 1 TRACK-J):947-50.
16. Healthcare SM: J of N and, 2016 undefined. Evidence of health risks associated with prolonged standing at work for health care professionals. *innovationaljournals.com* [Internet]. [cited 2025 Aug 23]; Available from: <https://innovationaljournals.com/index.php/ijnh/article/view/663>
17. Yasobant S, Health PRIJMP, 2015 undefined. Health of the healthcare professionals: A risk assessment study on work-related musculoskeletal disorders in a tertiary hospital, Chennai, India. *pdfs.semanticscholar.org* [Internet]. [cited 2025 Aug 23];(2). Available from: <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/9c3e/8e8c08415213a51cac49a2046ff2fce46894.pdf>
18. Ijsrset NG, 2016 undefined. Work related Musculoskeletal disorders among healthcare professional and their preventive measure: a report. *researchgate.net* [Internet]. [cited 2025 Aug 23]; Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Ganer-Naveen/publication/306263026_Work-Related_Musculoskeletal_Disorders_among_Healthcare_Professional_and_their_Preventive_Measure_A_Report/links/57b5726308aeddbf36e70b71/Work-Related-Musculoskeletal-Disorders-among-Healthcare-Professional-and-their-Preventive-Measure-A-Report.pdf
19. Bernardes RA, Caldeira S, Parreira P, Sousa LB, Apóstolo J, Almeida IF, et al. Foot and ankle disorders in nurses exposed to prolonged standing environments: A scoping review. *journals.sagepub.com* [Internet]. 2023 Mar 1 [cited 2025 Aug 23];71(3):101-16. Available from: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/21650799221137646>
20. Owie H, Apanga P. Occupational health hazards prevailing among healthcare workers in developing countries. 2016 [cited 2025 Aug 23]; Available from: <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/doi/full/10.5555/20163350994>
21. Work JM, 2002 undefined. Health risks associated with prolonged standing. *journals.sagepub.com* [Internet]. 2002 [cited 2025 Aug 23];19(2):201-5. Available from: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.3233/WOR-2002-00255>
22. Waters TR, Dick RB. Evidence of health risks associated with prolonged standing at work and intervention effectiveness. *Wiley Online Libr* [Internet]. 2015 May 1 [cited 2025 Aug 23];40(3):148-65. Available from: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/rnj.166>
23. Hess P, Athanasiadis D, ... NL... AJ of, 2024 undefined. Preventing surgeon work-related musculoskeletal disorders: a pilot study of the Comprehensive Operating Room Ergonomics (CORE) program. *research.aota.org* [Internet]. [cited 2025 Aug 23]; Available from: <https://research.aota.org/ajot/article-abstract/78/5/7805205090/25934>
24. Rodriguez JS, Méndez JAJ, Haro FB. Analysis of Ergonomic Aspects in the Surgery Field: Surgeons' Appraisals. *Springer* [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2025 Aug 23];192-200. Available from: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-99-0942-1_19

25. Janki S, Mulder EEAP, IJzermans JNM, Tran TCK. Ergonomics in the operating room. Springer [Internet]. 2017 Jun 1 [cited 2025 Aug 23];31(6):2457-66. Available from: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00464-016-5247-5>
26. Schlüssel A, surgery JMC in colon and rectal, 2019 undefined. Ergonomics and musculoskeletal health of the surgeon. thieme-connect.com [Internet]. 2019 [cited 2025 Aug 23];32(6):424-34. Available from: <https://www.thieme-connect.com/products/all/doi/10.1055/s-0039-1693026>
27. Durden AA, Newton C. Musculoskeletal injuries in cross-speciality surgeons: a survey of UK-based doctors. Springer [Internet]. 2023 Aug 1 [cited 2025 Aug 23];17(4):1797-802. Available from: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11701-023-01601-2>
28. Aldawsari SA, Alhammad AH, Dyab A, Alanazi S. A Study of the Prevalence of Low Back Pain and Associated Risk Factors Among Surgical Staff in Sudair Area , Saudi Arabia A Study of the Prevalence of Low Back Pain and Associated Risk Factors Among Surgical Staff in Sudair Area , Saudi Arabia. 2018;(December 2020).
29. Almaghrabi A, Alsharif F. Prevalence of Low Back Pain and Associated Risk Factors among Nurses at King Abdulaziz University Hospital. 2021;
30. Hospital J, Raza A, Zulfiqar A, Ijaz A, Naseer MB, Zahra SA. Prevalence of Lower Back Pain Among Doctors Working in Jinnah Hospital , Lahore. 2021;1(1).
31. Emam D Al, Denewar K. Egyptian Journal of Community Medicine Prevalence and Occupational Risk Factors of Low Back Pain among Health Care Workers in Operating Rooms at Mansoura University Main Hospital. 2023;1:3-10.
32. Nair RS, P JA. Prevalence and risk factors associated with low back pain among nurses in a tertiary care hospital in south India. 2020;6(1):301-6.
33. Yizengaw MA, Mustofa SY, Ashagrie HE. Prevalence and factors associated with work-related musculoskeletal disorder among health care providers working in the operation room. Ann Med Surg [Internet]. 2021;72(November):102989. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amsu.2021.102989>
34. Janki S, Tran TCK, Mulder EEAP. Ergonomics among operation theater staff in the operating room. 2017;2457-66.
35. Tolu S, Basaran B. Work-related musculoskeletal disorders in anesthesiologists: A cross-sectional study on prevalence and risk factors. Ann Med Res. 2019;26(7):1406.
36. Vural F, Sutsunbuloglu E. Ergonomics: an important factor in the operating room. J Perioper Pract. 2016;26(7-8):174-8.
37. Vural F, Sutsunbuloglu E. Ergonomics: An Important Factor in the Operating Room. J Perioper Pract [Internet]. 2016 Jul 1 [cited 2025 Aug 23];26(7-8):174-8. Available from: </doi/pdf/10.1177/1750458916026007-804?download=true>
38. Raghavendra Rao RS. Ergonomical aspects of anaesthetic practice. Indian J Anaesth. 2016;60(5):306-11.
39. Held J. Ergonomics in Anaesthesia Ergonomics in Anaesthesia 1. 1996; Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3929/ethz-b-000299255>